

reduction was obtained (see figure). That linear relationship can be expected under moderate disease pressure.

Although lesions may reach the same height, extent of lesion area may differ with weather conditions.

No significant yield reduction was found when RLH was less than 20%. If lesion reached the 3d sheath from the sheath bearing the flag leaf, and if RLH was about 30%, a significant yield loss was seen.

Additional loss would occur during milling if yield reduction in paddy rice was over 10% (USA data). A 46% yield loss is possible in milled rice if ShB lesion reaches 90% of RLH. $\mathcal{S}$

Relation between relative height of the uppermost ShB lesion and yield reduction in paddy rice (observations from national reports).

Pest Control and Management

INSECTS

Alang-alang gall midge potential as an alternate host for parasitoids

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Alang-alang *Imperata cylindrica* is a natural weed on the dikes of lowland ricefields. The Alang-alang gall midge (AGM) *Orseoliella javanica* Kieffer is its most important insect pest. In hilly and highland regions (altitude: 300-800 m), where the dikes on one side are 1-1.5 m high and 20-40 m long, AGM is abundant, especially where the weed is regularly cut for cattle feed.

Although the rice gall midge (RGM) *Orseolia oryzae* (Wood-Mason) does not attack Alang-alang and the AGM does not attack rice, both belong to the family Cecidomyiidae. Alang-alang with AGM in the RGM habitat does not directly affect RGM. But AGM may be an important alternate host of RGM parasitoids. In mountainous regions, RGM infestation is commonly low.

Six species of hymenopterous parasitoids of RGM have been found in Java and Bali, but only three are important: *Platygaster oryzae* (egg-larval

parasitoid), *Neanastatus oryzae* (pupal parasitoid), and *Propicroscytus mirificus* (syn. *Obtusiclava oryzae*) (larval parasitoid). *P. oryzae* and *N. oryzae* are commonly present in ricefields. Parasitism rates may reach 95% for *P. oryzae* and 50% for *N. oryzae*.

The life cycle of *P. oryzae*, in general, synchronizes with the life cycle of RGM (28-32 d). To study the biology of the RGM parasitoids, 1,032 samples of AGM were taken from 9 locations in West Java during 9 mo in 1983-84. Parasitoids, particularly larval and

1. Fluctuation of Alang-alang GM and its parasitoids in 7 locations in West Java, Jul 1983-Mar 1984. Figures above the columns indicate number of silvershoots taken in 1 h of monthly sampling time.

pupal, were present in AGM and were often found where the insect occurred (Fig. 1). The life cycles of the larval and pupal parasitoids are relatively the same as those which live in RGM (Fig. 2). The life cycle of *P. oryzae* synchronizes with the life cycle of the host. The life cycle of AGM is relatively longer (5-7 wk) than that of RGM (4-5 wk); the life cycle of *P. oryzae* on AGM is also longer than that on RGM (Fig. 2).

Based on biology and behavior, the *Platygaster* sp., which occurs as a dominant parasitoid of AGM, is now considered the complex of the *P. oryzae* of RGM. It attacks larvae of RGM, but attacks pupae of AGM because the parasite deposits eggs only when silvershoots of AGM emerge. ♀

2. Time of emergence of rice GM parasitoids.

Response of leaffolder (LF) *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* G. to extracts of resistant *Oryza sativa* and *O. brachyantha*

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Extracts of rice and wild rice cultivars with LF resistance were obtained by steam distillation of leaves followed by diethyl ether extraction. The oily extract was diluted with acetone.

Freshly laid eggs were dipped in a 2,000-ppm solution and excess liquid drained. The eggs were incubated in petri dishes lined with moistened filter paper and the number of hatched and unhatched eggs recorded.

To assess larval response, 15-cm-diam petri dishes were divided into 6 compartments labeled alphabetically clockwise. Leaf pieces dipped in each variety's extract were placed in A, C, and E compartments; leaf cuts dipped in acetone were placed in compartments B, D, and F. Twenty-four 1st-instar larvae were placed at the center of each dish. After 24 h, the larvae settling on each leaf piece were counted.

Three-hour-starved 3d-4th instar larvae were offered leaves treated with the diluted oily extract and larval mortality determined.

TKM6 extract significantly reduced hatching, 57% unhatched eggs compared to only 8% unhatched eggs for the solvent alone (Table 1). Cultivars Kamalbhog, Darukasail, and TKM6 showed 32-36% larval mortality, significantly greater than the 2% mortality in control. The odor of TN1

did not influence orientation or settling response of the larvae, but on other cultivars, more insects responded to the odor of the control (Table 2).

Based on antibiosis, most of the observed cultivars are LF resistant. The chemicals are active against LF eggs and larvae. ♀

Table 1. Effects of extracts obtained from rice and wild rice varieties on LF. IRRI, 1986.

Source of extract	Accession no.	Unhatched eggs (%)	Larval mortality (%)
<i>O. brachyantha</i>	101231	24 b	16 bc
<i>O. brachyantha</i>	101233	35 b	12 bcd
<i>O. brachyantha</i>	101234	39 b	8 d
<i>O. sativa</i>			
Darukasail	45493	20 b	32 a
Kamalbhog	49020	30 b	34 a
TKM6 (resistant check)	237	57 a	36 a
TN1 (susceptible check)	105	22 b	4 cd
Control (solvent only)	--	8 c	0 d

Table 2. Attraction of LF to leaves treated with steam distillate oils obtained from *Oryza* species. IRRI, 1986.

Cultivar	Accession no.	Insects (no.) after 24 h		Difference
		Treated with extract	Control	
<i>O. brachyantha</i>	101231	22	63	41**
<i>O. brachyantha</i>	101233	32	44	12**
<i>O. brachyantha</i>	101234	39	46	7 ns
<i>O. sativa</i>				
Darukasail	45493	24	47	23**
Kamalbhog	49020	20	51	31**
TKM6	237	10	60	44**
TN1	105	37	57	19 ns